

Relationships between VSD programs and industrial transformation in Bangladesh

Skills for Industry Policy Brief Bangladesh #2 (2021)

At a glance:

This policy brief explains how employers perceive qualifications from Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) institutes in Bangladesh. It focuses on the Ready-Made Garment (RMG) and Pharmaceutical sectors. These industrial sectors have embraced transformation – by changing their organizational structures, increasing product complexity, and, in particular, upgrading production technologies. But do TVET qualifications give workers the right skills for this transformation? There are only a few TVET programs for the RMG sector, but they are not highly regarded. Therefore, few employees in RMG have TVET qualifications. There are no TVET programs specifically tailored for the Pharmaceutical sector. In these circumstances, both the RMG and Pharma sectors either hire employees with previous work experience, or they train their employees informally on-the-job (senior colleagues train junior colleagues, or machine suppliers conduct training). Nevertheless, employers would value TVET qualifications, especially for low and mid-level employees, if they were better suited to industry needs. Therefore, this policy brief recommends helping TVET institutions and industrialists work together to make TVET programs more effective and relevant to the needs of changing industries. It also recommends making TVET programs more valued in wider society. Finally, it also recommends improving on-the-job training.

Introduction:

Usually, industrial transformation and the development of TVET programs happen in tandem, since technological change requires employees to have new skills – specifically high-tech and service-oriented skills. The key function of TVET is to produce a skilled workforce that matches labor market requirements. There is a significant positive correlation between skills development (soft and hard) and a productive workforce (King and Palmer, 2008) and high employment (Karki, 2011). However, in developing countries, skills training does not reflect these industrial requirements (UNIDO, 2017).

This policy brief presents the initial findings from case studies carried out in the RMG and Pharmaceutical sectors in Bangladesh (9 and 8 companies respectively). The case studies are part of the “Skills for Industry” project, designed to examine the contribution of TVET programs to industrial growth and transformation of manufacturing companies. This brief follows from an earlier contextual analysis and survey of the companies, from which a first policy brief was produced, available here: <https://phzh.ch/en/Research/skills-for-industry/publications/>.

Bangladesh is focusing on transitioning from agricultural to industrial development in order to grow the economy and become a middle-income country by 2024. To this end, export-oriented industries, especially the RMG and Pharmaceutical industries, are undergoing major transformation in terms of technology and product design. As a result, day by day, the demand for trained and

skilled workers is increasing. However, the number of manufacturing employees who have undertaken TVET training remains negligible in the RMG sector, and non-existent for the Pharmaceutical industry, where there are no TVET programs tailored to the sector's needs.

Earlier survey data from this project showed that there was little to no formal on-the-job training. However, this case study found that companies do in fact offer some informal on-the-job training, or bring machine operators in to train operators, supervisors and technicians.

On the basis of these findings, this policy brief suggests five ways to improve TVET training programs and on-the-job training in the RMG and Pharma sectors in Bangladesh.

Findings:

1. RMG and Pharmaceutical companies have embraced technological transformation

Most companies in our case studies are embracing technological and organizational transformation to survive in the changing market, as well as to create new markets. This has changed the quantity and quality of garments and medicines. Garment factories are producing a greater range of fashionable clothes; pharmaceutical companies can produce 1 to 3 new drugs per year (subject to market demand, managers' preferences and the latest approval of the drug authority), without much human labor involved. Meeting demand is key to surviving in the market.

Different styles of product emerge to meet client demand, and the price becomes higher. Without adapting to these changes, you cannot survive in the market. If you are to compete with other companies to survive, then you must change the machinery over time unless it is not possible to work at this time. ~ Senior manager of a garment company. (6 out of 9 garment companies expressed similar views.)

In both the RMG and Pharma sectors, manual machines are being replaced with automated machines. For example, sweater factories have been completely automated, meaning that common tasks for general workers, such as cutting yarn in the oven factory, are now done by machines.

The advantage of the auto machine is that it needs no 'helper', and it saves yarn as well...

In the pharmaceutical sector, everything from product processing to packaging - washing, labeling, coating, blistering, capsule filling - is becoming automated. With dynamic new machines, it is now possible to produce many more products in a short period of time:

Previously all the machines were manual. Automated machines are now available everywhere. Everything from product processing to packaging happens without the touch of a hand. Suppose five workers were required to do one task. Now it can be done with only two operators on the auto machine. One starts the process and the other takes the product delivery at the end of the process.

Whilst automation is the general trend, two garment companies report that there has not been much change in terms of product lines. They are still producing the same clothing items - shirts, blazers, pants, sweaters - although new designs are constantly being added to keep up with demand.

Buyers' demands are changing day by day so we have to update our production, keeping up with changing demand. Our goal is to meet buyers' demands.

2. Garment and Pharmaceutical companies value previous work experience more than pre-employment TVET training

Company employers in both sectors value previous work experience. RMG companies value previous work experience more than TVET qualifications. In fact, few employees in the RMG sector have relevant TVET qualifications (apart from technicians). Pharmaceutical companies value previous work experience because there simply are no TVET programs tailored to the sector's needs.

It is generally believed that general workers and operators with previous work experience will be able to adapt to change more easily than inexperienced employees.

If an employee does not have previous work experience, it will take longer for them to adapt to these changes; but if they have previous work experience or have had on-the-job training at a different company ["outside training"], they will find it easier to adapt to these changes.

RMG companies, in particular, are not concerned about a skills shortage amongst staff. They believe that, although productivity might temporarily falter, their experienced operators and technicians can quickly adapt to change.

At first, when a new machine is introduced, production is slightly reduced, but after a few days it increases.

However, sometimes even the adaptable, experienced employees struggle to operate a new machine. In such cases, the company will seek to hire, on higher salaries, new employees with the requisite experience and/or skills (with/without TVET qualifications) to operate the machine in question.

3. Garment and Pharmaceutical companies value their own on-the-job training more than pre-employment TVET training

We asked companies whether they agreed or disagreed with the statement: 'On-the-job training is more important than any TVET qualifications achieved prior to recruitment.' In the Garment industry, 71% of production managers and 57% of senior managers agreed with this statement with respect to **higher-level** employees (29% and 43% expressed no opinion, respectively). 71% of production managers and 57% of senior managers agreed with respect to **mid-level** employees (29% and 43% expressed no opinion, respectively). In the Pharma industry, 66% of senior managers and 60% of production managers agreed with respect to **higher-level** employees (17% and 0% expressed no opinion, 17% and 40% disagree, respectively). 67% of senior managers and 40% of production managers agreed with respect to **mid-level** (33% and 40% expressed no opinion, 0% and 20% disagree, respectively).

*Overall, this shows that, across both sectors, around two thirds of employers prefer on-the-job training for employees, especially for **higher-level** employees. However, quite a few also called for new/improved TVET for **mid-level** employees.*

Because there are no tailored TVET programs for the Pharmaceutical sector, and those for RMG are not highly valued, companies in both sectors conduct informal on-the-job training in-house. When a new product is introduced, the production manager first explains its design to the supervisor or line chief. The latter then instructs his subordinate operators and general workers. In the Garments sector, one third of senior and production managers say that within 1-2 days the workers get the hang of it. Alternatively, when new machinery is acquired, the suppliers install it and train the supervisors and technicians, who in turn train operators and helpers, who then "gradually become accustomed to this change."

In the Pharmaceutical sector, most employees in mid- and higher- level production have professional degrees (B.Sc or M.Sc in Pharmacy (mostly) or chemistry). Operators and below must have a H.S.C

(Higher Secondary school Certificate). Since there are no tailored TVET programs, Pharmaceutical companies have to arrange some on-the-job training for employees. But they would like to see more TVET training options for machine operators and maintenance technicians.

There are some sophisticated machines which cannot be left in the hands of operators who are not trained/skilled. Technical and Vocational Education gives them some technical knowledge. The problem, however, is that diploma engineers do not like to work as operators. The Pharmaceutical industry expects more technical education for machine operators and maintenance technicians.

Conclusion:

These case studies of the RMG and Pharmaceutical sectors in Bangladesh show that technological change is being embraced, but existing TVET training opportunities are not regarded as particularly helpful in adapting to these changes. Previous work experience and on-the-job training (by senior staff or machine suppliers) are considered more relevant than previous institutional training. This means we need to consider how to improve the relevance of TVET, as well as how to improve and formalize on-the-job training.

Recommendations:

1. Make TVET programs more effective and practical. For example, arrange appropriate time allocations for the practical part of TVET programs in coordination with factories.

2. Ensure TVET training matches the skills requirements of industry.
3. Take various steps to make TVET programs more acceptable in society. For example, informing students and their parents at the lower secondary level about the available TVET programs, as well as encouraging companies to hire qualified workers.
4. Formally institutionalize the training imparted within the factory.
5. Keep experienced staff as trainers.

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About: This policy brief is part of an ongoing series and based on research conducted within the “Skills for Industry” project (phzh.ch/skillsforindustry). The project is funded by the Swiss Programmes for Research on Global Issues for Development.

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Published by: University of Teacher Education Zurich & BRAC University, in Zurich (Switzerland) & Dhaka (Bangladesh)

DOI: doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5005055
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